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%load data
Mouse_function_data = '..\Function data\14d REGN\*.txt'

%view directory
directory = dir(Mouse_function_data)

%storage for loop iterations

%zeros creates an empty vector of zeros that I can store peak torque values
%in - I set them to numel(directory) because that's the column size I
%wanted, the 1 is just for making it a 1xn column

peak_torque_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
ROTD_vals = zeros(numel(directory),1)
file_names = cell(numel(directory),1)

%Looping through files

%number of files is assigned to directory
for file_counter = 1 : numel(directory)

    folder_name = directory(file_counter).folder
    file_name = directory(file_counter).name
    full_name = fullfile(folder_name, file_name)

    %read table during each iteration
    t = readtable(full_name)
    justforce = t.FilteredForce
    peak_torque = max(justforce)

    %correction factor for peak torque
    avg_base_force = mean(justforce(1:2000))
    peak_torque1 = peak_torque-avg_base_force
    corrected_force_vector = justforce-avg_base_force
    normalized_force_vector = corrected_force_vector/peak_torque1

    %aurora sampling rate, make time vector

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sampling_rate = 850/8500
time_vector = [0:sampling_rate:849.99]'

%extracting time and force at indices of interest (20%-80% of torque
%development) technically, I don't need to use corrected force vector
%here since I'm measuring changes in force, not raw force
pulling_time= time_vector(2600:2900)
pulling_force= normalized_force_vector(2600:2900)

%Make best fit line eq and pull slope - this is ROTD
best_fit = polyfit(pulling_time,pulling_force,1)
ROTD = best_fit(1)

%converting ROTD into mNm/1s
%sampling frequency is 850ms/8500samples = .1ms/sample - so right now,
%units are xmNm/.1ms
%convert to seconds
%1s = 1000ms, .1ms = 10000
%ROTD_corrected = ROTD*10000

%filling zeros vectors with torque and ROTD values

peak_torque_vals(file_counter) = peak_torque1
ROTD_vals(file_counter) = ROTD*10000
file_names{file_counter} = file_name

end

%Find way to display peak torque in a table
peak_torque_vals

final_vals = table(file_names, peak_torque_vals, ROTD_vals)

%for excel export
filename = 'Raw and normalized ROTDs.xlsx'
writetable(final_vals,filename,'Sheet',1,'Range','M12')

%ROTD units are mili Newton meters/.0411ms
%24.33 conversion factor to make /1ms

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